

Analysis of Land Use Land Cover Detection Using Remote Sensing and GIS of Coimbatore Region, Tamil Nadu

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Abstract The study's main aim is to analyze the land use changes of the Coimbatore Corporation for the period of 2017 and 2023. The temporal analysis was conducted using two satellite images and multiple vector data. ArcGIS Pro image classification and machine learning packages are used to capture building footprints and road networks. The satellite images are classified into four major classes: water, crops, trees, built-up, flooded vegetation, range land and bare land. Further, study shows that there was a major decreased in crops (-6.42%), bare land (-1.13%) and range land (-0.2%) and a major built up (4.81%), flooded vegetation (0.302%), water (1.14%) and trees (1.09%) has increased in land use from 2017-2023. The population growth increases the built area and this is the reason for the change of LULC classes. ArcGIS Pro ML-based segmentation and supervised classification method are used to classify images and capture vector data. The change detection of LULC analysis shows an increase in residential, commercial, and Industrial areas due to rapid urbanization.

Keywords Land Use Land Cover, Remote Sensing and GIS

Introduction

Urbanization refers to the process of increasing population concentration in urban areas. Urban areas are characterized by higher population densities, extensive infrastructure, and a variety of economic and social activities (Baig et al., 2022). Because of increase in population the land is occupied and it changes the land cover pattern. Changes in Land Use and Land Cover (LULC) affect the biosphere, climate, and terrestrial environment, but most importantly, it affect the human social context (Kumar and Agrawal, 2023). It is widely acknowledged that identifying and evaluating past and present changes in land use patterns. It is crucial to comprehend and resolve socioeconomic and environmental issues (Gule et al., 2023). With the development of Earth observation technology, applications for detecting past LULC change have emerged. Prior research was artificially interpreted using satellite imagery and supplementary field observations. Remote Sensing (RS) and Geographical Information System (GIS) technologies are commonly applied in monitoring LULC changes (Pandey and Kumari, 2023). LULC is a major significance for regional and global environmental change, making it a frontier and hotspot of international research that has attracted the attention of the researcher worldwide (Kafy et al., 2021). It is possible to assess and monitor LULC changes at different spatial and multi-temporal levels. Hence, this research area objectives includes: To analysis the 2017 and 2023 land use changes of Coimbatore corporation; Classify and Quantify the Land use change for 2017 and 2023; Analyze and evaluate the impact of land use changes in different LULC classes and find the growth pattern.

Study Area

Coimbatore city, is one of the metropolitan cities in Tamil Nadu located in India as shown in fig: 1. This study area spans a total of 257.04 sqkm and is situated between latitude 11°00'16''N and longitude 76°57'20''E. It is located in the Western Ghats' rain shadow area with moderate temperature. The climate in Coimbatore City is sub-humid. Coimbatore, known as the 'Manchester of South India', boasts a thriving textile industry that serves as a significant contributor to the city's production and economy. This industry flourishes due to its close proximity to cotton fields in the neighboring villages, allowing for a seamless supply chain and fostering a robust manufacturing sector in the city. Recently Coimbatore areas, the population of region in 2023 is 4,100,000; however, the 2021 census has been postponed and the previous census was completed in 2011. The natural landforms are combined with deep weather, and shallow pediments, which is an ideal morphological formation for agricultural activities in the area.

Figure: 1 Study area located map

Materials and Methods

Methodology

Figure 2 shows the high-level methodology adopted for this research study.

Figure 2: Methodology

Data Collection and Data Pre-Processing

In order to simulate and forecast the spatiotemporal patterns of LULC in Coimbatore, Tamilnadu, India, the work is divided into three parts. In the first stage, LULC layers for various years were prepared and remote sensing images encompassing the research region were gathered. In the second stage, LULCC was analyzed. The variables influencing LULC changes were identified in the final step of the process, after which LULC was forecasted and simulated. The various kinds of temporal-based multispectral images remote sensing data from the Landsat dataset for the years 2017 & 2023 were collected and utilized in this study. A spatial and non-spatial database was designed to store collected spatial and non-spatial data in the required format. Collected vector data like corporation boundary, zone, and ward data are overlapped with SOI data, and distractions are corrected and stored in spatial database. The Satellite images are processed using ArcGIS Pro to remove image distortions, composite bands, mosaic, and extract raster images using the mask (Easwer et al., 2022). Different additional image enhancement techniques are performed to improve image visualization and object visibility. Image Classification is the process of classifying its pixel into different land use classes (Baig et al., 2022). Based on the image spectral reflectance or emissivity characteristics, image pixels are grouped together in classes that are assumed to represent specific categories of earth features. A hybrid supervised technique is used to classify the image to require land use classes. Image Extraction is the process of converting classified images to vector data to improve the accuracy of the data. ArcGIS Image Service with Deep Learning ML technique used to capture building footprints and road networks (Mahamud et al., 2019). The vector data are overlaid in high-resolution satellite image service, and different geometric operations like split, merge, explode, smooth, and topology techniques are performed to improve the

accuracy of the data. Analysis of LULC changes of different overlay operations are performed to correct geometry and merge collected other spatial and non-spatial data with land use data. This will help to improve the quality and accuracy of the land use data. Accuracy assessment is the fundamental step for land use and land cover classification to avoid errors. High resolution satellite image service from ArcGIS Online, Google Earth, and field validation is carried out to improve the accuracy of the land use classification.

Results and Discussions

The study emphasizes the importance of analyzing changes in land cover and land use for predicting the urbanization of Coimbatore regions. After the classifications of LULC shown in **Figure 3 & 4**: It is analyzed that the different categories of LULC pattern has shift major that pin out during the years (2017 and 2023) **Table 1**: shows the area and percentage calculated. While analyzing the study area, the water bodies has increased the area of 22.62 sq km to 53.7 sq km from 2017 and 2023 the representing a percentage of (1.02-2.43%). The area of trees has increased by 29.59 sqkm and 46.58 sqkm, representing a percentage of (1.34-2.109%). Another area of flooded vegetation has increased the area of 0.072 sqkm and 0.37sqkm, represents the area percentage of (0.003-0.016%). The sudden change of built up area has increased has the area of 1649.94 sqkm and 1756.07sqkm, represent a percentage of (74.73-79.54%). Next, Crops land area has suddenly decreased the area of 422.94 sqkm and 273.95 sqkm, representing a percentage of (74.73-79.54%). Furthermore, **chart 1**: identified the changes from (2017-2023) bare land and range land has decreased the area of 2.15-1.02 sqkm and 80.55-76.17 sqkm while the represent the percentage of (0.097-0.046%) and (3.65-3.45%). Finally, the land use change detection is analyzed and revealed a major decrease in crops area.

Figure 3: Land use land cover changes 2017

Figure 4: Land use land cover changes of detection 2023

Table 1: Classification of Land Use Land Cover Changes

LULC Classification	2017		2023	
	Area sq km	Percentage (%)	Area sq km	Percentage (%)
Water	22.617	1.024381	53.7	2.432208
Trees	29.59	1.340206	46.58	2.109726
Flooded Vegetation	0.072	0.003261	0.374	0.016939
Crops	422.94	19.15602	273.95	12.40789
Built up	1649.94	74.72994	1756.07	79.53684
Bare Ground	2.154	0.09756	1.02	0.046198
Rangeland	80.5464	3.64815	76.17	3.449931

Chart 1: Land Use Land Cover changes (2017-2023)

Conclusion

This study shows that there was a major decreased in crops (-6.42%), bare land (-1.13%) and range land (-0.2%) and a major built up (4.81%), flooded vegetation (0.302%), water (1.14%) and trees (1.09%) has increased in land use from 2017-2023. The population growth which increases the built area is a reason for the sudden change for LULC classes. Recreational land use was increased due to laws imposed by the government. Geospatial tools are highly effective in detecting and analyzing land use changes, predicting future trends, and analyzing existing patterns.

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